

Thyroid Disorders among Reproductive Age Group Women with Abnormal Uterine Bleeding

Farijan Kaladi¹, Bindhu K.M.²¹Junior Resident, Department of OBG, Govt. Medical College, Kottayam, Kerala²Additional Professor, Department of OBG, Govt. Medical College, Kottayam, Kerala

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Farijan Kaladi

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Abstract:**Background:** AUB is any abnormal uterine bleeding in the absence of any palpable pelvic pathology and demonstrable extra genital cause. AUB is responsible for 10% of gynaecological complaints. The objective of this study was to assess the patterns of thyroid disorders among reproductive age group women with abnormal uterine bleeding.**Methods:** The present study was conducted in the department of obstetrics and gynecology, Govt medical college Kottayam, Kerala, India 400 women of reproductive age group between 18-45 years women with menstrual disorders like heavy menstrual bleeding, irregular cycles, prolonged bleeding, light bleeding, frequent cycles infrequent cycles and quantitative determination of T3, T4 and TSH values.**Results:** About 400 women participated in the study in which most of the subjects belong to mean age of 32 years. Maximum patients included in parity 2 about 185.

Commonest bleeding pattern is heavy and prolonged bleeding that is 26 and 26.6% respectively. Out of 400 patients, 105 patients had thyroid abnormality. Of which 54 were diagnosed as subclinical hypothyroidism, 29 had hypothyroidism and 13 had hyperthyroidism 9 patients had subclinical hyperthyroidism. The frequent menstrual symptoms associated with hypothyroidism and subclinical hypothyroidism was heavy and prolonged bleeding. Light and short bleeding pattern detected in patient with hyperthyroidism.

Conclusion: Any type of menstrual disorder should be considered as a possible presenting symptom of thyroid dysfunction thyroid assessment deemed necessary in such cases, so that we can treat patients at the earliest and prevent morbidities in later life.**Keywords:** Abnormal Uterine Bleeding, Hypothyroidism, Hyperthyroidism, Subclinical Hypothyroidism, Subclinical Hyperthyroidism, Euthyroid.

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Introduction

Abnormal uterine bleeding is defined as any type of bleeding that is abnormal in volume, frequency, duration and periodicity. Frequent complaints include heavy and prolonged menstrual bleeding with or without pain, passage of clots, fatigue and lethargy. Womens Health Related Quality of Life (HRQL) worsens in dealing with such bleeding and the consequences of excessive blood loss. AUB is one of the frequent presentation in gynaecological OPD, occurs in 9-14% women between menarche to menopause. Menstrual abnormality is primarily a disorder of hypothalamic- pituitary- Ovarian axis either directly or indirectly by their effect on target organs. Other than the reproductive hormones endocrinological disturbances also play a crucial role for etiopathogenesis of AUB. Amongst the endocrinological causes, thyroid hormone has wide range of effect on the development, growth and metabolism of every organ system of human body.[1] Timely detection of thyroid dysfunction in

women with AUB and its proper management can prevent unnecessary surgical interventions and helps to reduce financial burden and improves the quality of life. Hence this study is undertaken to evaluate the thyroid dysfunction in women with abnormal uterine bleeding.[2]

Laboratory Evaluation

The diagnosis of hypothyroidism is based in the combination of clinical context and laboratory tests. A number of factors affect the levels of TSH, total T4 and total T3. But the serum levels of free T4 remain normal in these circumstances and provide a better assessment of thyroid function. Patients who have primary hypothyroidism have elevated TSH and low FT4 and FT3. TPO antibodies are found in many patients who have hashimoto's thyroiditis. A repeatedly elevated TSH, between 4 and 15 mIU/mL, with normal FT4 and FT3 is suggestive of subclinical hypothyroidism.[3]

Table 1:

FREE T3	FREE T4	TSH	DIAGNOSIS
Normal	Normal	Normal	Euthyroid Status
Elevated	Elevated	Low	Hyperthyroidism
Low	Low	Elevated	Hypothyroidism
Normal	Normal	Elevated	Subclinical Hypothyroidism
Normal	Normal	Low	Subclinical Hyperthyroidism

Thyroid Hormone Reference Value

1. TSH-0.5 -4.7mU/L
2. T3-0.92-2.78nmol/L
3. T4-58-140nmol/L

Materials and Methods

Type of study: Cross sectional study

Period of study: 1 year from 11-10-22

Study setting: Govt. Medical College Kottayam

Sample size: 400 patients

Study population: Reproductive age group women with abnormal uterine bleeding attending in Gynaecology OPD

Inclusion Criteria

1. Age group 18-45 years
2. With any of the following menstrual disturbances (heavy menstrual bleeding, irregular bleeding, amenorrhoea).

Exclusion Criteria

1. Pregnancy and associated complications.
2. Women who are using intrauterine contraceptive device (IUCD)
3. Women who are on any hormonal preparation (eg: oral contraceptive pills)
4. Women on thyroid replacement therapy
5. Presence of pelvic pathology like fibroids, polyps or cervical growths.
6. Known case of genital malignancy
7. Pelvic inflammatory disease.
8. Diagnosed case of Polycystic Ovarian Disease (PCOD).
9. H/O bleeding disorder
10. Taking any medications like steroids, anticoagulants, antithyroid medications and cytotoxic drugs.

Data Collection Tools

Out patient's records, in patient's records, case proforma. A validated semi structured interviewer administered proforma will be used to collect relevant Information from the Study Participants.

Study Procedure

Study will be started after the approval of institutional review board. This is a cross sectional study. All patients included in the study after satisfying

inclusion and exclusion criteria. Written informed consent in the local language will be obtained from patients. Data are collected from gynaecological outpatient department of Kottayam Medical College.

The demographic profile of all eligible patients is recorded under the following headings, study serial no, age, contact no. And they were undergone a thorough history taking regarding their age, parity, present history, past history, medical history, any previous surgical history, treatment history & a detailed menstrual history like pattern, onset, duration, interval and amount of bleeding and other associated menstrual complaints and also complaints related to thyroid dysfunction. The method of contraception also noted, since intrauterine contraceptive devices are associated with increased menstrual blood loss.

A thorough clinical examination including general physical examination, systemic, gynaecological like bimanual pelvic and speculum examination, search for polyps protruding through the cervical os and for enlargement or tenderness of the uterus or adnexae, neck examination with special reference to thyroid dysfunction.

All these patients are subjected to routine investigations like blood counts, urine examination for sugar, albumin, microscopy, bleeding time, clotting time to rule out coagulation defect and ultrasound (abdominopelvic usg). Then all patients will be subjected for T3, T4 and TSH Estimation in their serum. T3 and T4 were assayed by chemiluminescent immunoassay. These tests will be done in random blood sample as the variation in TSH secretion due to circadian rhythm with a peak at 1.00hrs and nadir at 11 hrs is small and does not influence the timing of blood sampling.

The following are noted:

- Level of serum T3 FT3
- Level of serum T4 FT4
- Level of TSH

Patient will then be grouped into 5 categories

1. Euthyroid
2. Subclinical hypothyroid
3. Hypothyroid
4. Hyperthyroid
5. Subclinical hyperthyroid

Data Management and Analysis

Data was entered in Microsoft excel and analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 20.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp. IBM Corp. Categorical variables were expressed as frequency and numerical variable as mean. Pearson chi-square test was used to evaluate the association of various cat-

egorical variables like parity, family history and other clinical findings with the thyroid disorders.

Comparison of mean age, BMI and Hb were done using one-way ANOVA. For all these statistical interpretations, $p < 0.05$ was considered the threshold for statistical significance.

Results**Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Characters Age, BMI, and Hemoglobin**

Characteristic	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	400	18	45	32.77	7.676
BMI	400	16	35	23.92	4.233
Hemoglobin	400	8.00	13.00	11.06	1.172

Table 3: Frequencies of Each Variable

Variable	Status	Frequency	Percent
Parity	0	120	30.0
	1	75	18.8
	2	185	46.3
	3	20	5.0
Infertility	Yes	38	9.5
	No	362	90.5
Dysmenorrhea	Yes	140	35.0
	No	260	65.0
Family history	Yes	48	12.0
	No	352	88.0
Bulky uterus	Yes	13	3.3
	No	387	96.8

Table 4: Frequencies of Different Bleeding Patterns

Variable	Status	Frequency	Percent
Duration of flow	Prolonged	188	47.0
	Normal	144	36.0
	Shortened	68	17.0
Frequency	Frequent	39	9.8
	Normal	259	64.8
	Infrequent	102	25.5
Quantity of bleeding	Heavy	214	53.5
	Normal	135	33.8
	Light	51	12.8
Regularity	Absent	9	2.3
	Regular	312	78.0
	Irregular	79	19.8

Table 5: Distribution According To Different Thyroid Condition

Condition	Frequency	Percent
Hypothyroidism	29	7.2
Subclinical hypothyroidism	54	13.5
Hyperthyroidism	13	3.3
Subclinical hyperthyroidism	9	2.3
Euthyroidism	295	73.8

Table 6: Association of Various Factors with Different Thyroid Conditions

Factor	Stat us	Thyroid disorder					P value
		Hypothyroidism N (%)	Subclinical hypothyroidism N (%)	Hyperthyroidism N (%)	Euthyroidism N (%)	Subclinical hyperthyroidism N (%)	
Parity	0	13 (10.8)	20 (16.7)	0 (0.0)	82 (68.3)	5 (4.2)	0.012 *
	1	5 (6.7)	6 (8.0)	0 (0.0)	63 (84.0)	1 (1.3)	
	2	11 (5.9)	27 (14.6)	12 (6.5)	132 (71.4)	3 (1.6)	
	3	0 (0.0)	1 (5.0)	1 (5.0)	18 (90.0)	0 (0.0)	
Infertility	Yes	10 (26.3)	6 (15.8)	0 (0.0)	22 (57.9)	0 (0.0)	<0.001 *
	No	19 (5.2)	48 (13.3)	13 (3.6)	273 (75.4)	9 (2.5)	
Dysmenorrhea	Yes	14 (10.0)	23 (16.4)	3 (2.1)	99 (70.7)	1 (0.7)	0.14
	No	15 (5.8)	31 (11.9)	10 (3.8)	196 (75.4)	8 (3.1)	
Family history	Yes	8 (16.7)	13 (27.3)	0 (0.0)	26 (54.5)	1 (2.1)	0.001 *
	No	21 (6.0)	41 (11.6)	13 (3.7)	269 (76.4)	8 (2.3)	
Bulky uterus	Yes	3 (23.1)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	10 (76.9)	0 (0.0)	0.125
	No	26 (6.7)	54 (14.0)	13 (3.4)	285 (73.6)	9 (2.2)	

p value <0.05 is considered statistically significant. Pearson chi-square test

Inference

There is statistically significant association for parity, infertility and family history with the thyroid disorders. The proportion of Euthyroid were highest among the people with parity 3. About 26.3 %

of people with infertility had hypothyroidism while only 5.2% without infertility had hypothyroidism, this trend was reversed in case of Euthyroidism.

Similar trend was observed in case of family history too.

Table 7: Association of Various Pattern of Bleeding with Each Thyroid Disorders

Characteristics	Status	Thyroid disorder					P value
		Hypothyroidism	Subclinical hypothyroidism	Hyperthyroidism	Subclinical hyperthyroidism	Euthyroidism	
		N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	
Duration of flow	Prolonged	20 (10.6)	30 (16.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	138 (73.4)	<0.001 *
	Normal	9 (6.2)	22 (15.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	113 (78.5)	
	Shortened	0 (0.0)	2 (2.9)	13 (19.1)	9 (13.2)	44 (64.7)	
Frequency	Frequent	0 (0.0)	8 (20.5)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	31 (79.5)	0.016 *
	Normal	18 (6.9)	31 (12.0)	13 (5.0)	9 (3.5)	188 (72.6)	
	Infrequent	11 (10.8)	15 (14.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	76 (74.5)	
Quantity of bleeding	Heavy	24 (11.2)	31 (14.5)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.5)	158 (73.8)	<0.001 *
	Normal	5 (3.7)	20 (14.8)	0 (0.0)	4 (3.0)	106 (78.5)	
	Light	0 (0.0)	3 (5.9)	13 (25.5)	4 (7.8)	31 (60.8)	
Regularity	Absent	0 (0.0)	2 (22.2)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	7 (77.8)	0.07
	Regular	18 (5.8)	37 (11.9)	13 (4.2)	8 (2.6)	236 (75.6)	
	Irregular	11 (13.9)	15 (19.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (1.3)	52 (65.8)	

p value <0.05 is considered statistically significant. Pearson chi-square test

Inference

There is statistically significant association for Duration of flow, Frequency, Quantity of bleeding with the thyroid disorders. Among those with shortened duration flow the proportion of people

with Euthyroidism was lesser than prolonged and normal however there was an increase in the proportion of people with hyperthyroidism and subclinical hyperthyroidism.

Among people with frequent flow the proportion of

patients with subclinical hypothyroidism was higher than normal and infrequent. Among the people with normal flow proportion of people with Hyper and subclinical hyperthyroidism was higher than frequent an infrequent.

Among people with heavy or normal quantity of bleeding the proportion of people with hypo and subclinical hypothyroidism was higher than light bleeding, and proportion of people with hyperthyroidism was higher among people with light bleeding compared to heavy and normal bleeding.

Discussion

In this study we have taken reproductive age group patients between 18-45yrs majority of patient belongs to mean age of 32yrs. In the study by Bishal Raj Joshi et al.[4] obtained similar results in their study the mean age of patients 33+/-8 years according to the study conducted by Sharma p et al maximum number of patients in the age group 31-40 years.[5] in the study by Sangeeta Pahwa et al.[6] Tara et al.[7] and Sudha HC et al.[8] obtained similar results in their study that is maximum number of patients in 31-40 years of age group (42%, 34%, 40% respectively). So all the study suggest that AUB become common as age advances.

Multiparous women comprises the major part of our study population. The majority of the cases had a parity of 2 no-185 (46%) nulliparous 30% and parity one 18%. in a study carried out by Javed ali et al[9], majority of the cases had a parity of >/=2(43%) and 40%were nulliparous. Similarly in the study carried out by kumar AHS et al [10] most of them were para 2 (40%) and nulliparous 43%. in the study carried out by Singh pet almost all of the were parity 3 (36%) followed by parity 2 (34%). Multiparous women comprised the major part of our study population ie 280 out of the 400 patients (70%) most of the women affected by thyroid dysfunction were also multiparous (54.6) followed by nulliparous (31.7%).

There is statistically significant association between parity and thyroid disorders in our study. Similarly study by Sudha HC et al [8] and Tara et al [7] multiparous patients (83%, 42% respectively) were maximum. In the study by Sudha HC et al [8], though maximum patients were multiparous among those who attended OPD with AUB maximum thyroid dysfunction were found in nulliparous patients (54%)

In a study by Franks set al on the basis of TSH, T3and T4 values thyroid disorders are divided into hypothyroid, hyperthyroid, subclinical hypothyroid, subclinical hyperthyroid and euthyroid. 73% of (n=295) AUB patients were euthyroid (normal cohort) in thyroid dysfunction cohort 26.3% (n=105). Hypothyroidism is 29 (7.2%) subclinical hypothyroidism 54 (13.5%) hyperthyroidism [11] (3.3%),

subclinical hyperthyroidism is 9 (2.3%). Similar in study by Kundoor R et al [1], majority of thyroid disorder was subclinical hypothyroid 15% followed by hypothyroid 10% and hyperthyroid 2.5%, in a study by Sudha HC et al [8], euthyroid constitute 62% patients with hypothyroidism 12%, subclinical hypothyroidism in 16% and hyperthyroidism 2% in both study subclinical hypothyroid patients are in maximum followed by hypothyroid patients.

In a study conducted by Ezhil Rini et al, 79.5% of the patients with AUB were euthyroid whereas 20.5% has some form of thyroid dysfunction sub-clinical hypothyroidism was the most common thyroid dysfunction (15.5%) in this study followed by hypothyroidism (3.5%) only 1.5% patients had hyperthyroidism [12] in a study conducted by Thakur et al, 13.9% had hypothyroidism and 1.3% had hyperthyroidism [13].

Among the hypothyroid cases 8.8% had subclinical and 5.06% had overt hypothyroidism. Another study by Kumar AHS et al⁹ in which out of 200 cases 162 (81%) cases were euthyroid, 38 (19%) cases had thyroid dysfunction out of which 33 (16.5%) were hypothyroid and 5 (2.5%) were hyperthyroid. Among hypothyroid 21 cases (10.5%) were subclinical and 12 (6%) had overt hypothyroidism.

In the present study categorises the bleeding pattern according to the duration of flow, frequency, quantity of bleeding and regularity and studied about the association of different thyroid disorders with different AUB pattern. Finding suggests a statistically significant association of AUB with thyroid disorders. 26.6% patients were presented with prolonged bleeding per vaginum, 26% cases had heavy bleeding are the most common AUB pattern. If we consider individual thyroid dysfunction in hypothyroid 10.6% had prolonged bleeding 10.8% infrequent cycles, 11.2% cases had heavy bleeding 13.9% with irregular cycles. Likewise in subclinical hypothyroidism 16% had prolonged bleeding. 2.9% shortened flow, 20.5% had frequent cycles. 14.8% had heavy bleeding, absent cycles for 2 cases, 15 cases had irregular cycles.

In hyperthyroidism 13 cases had shortened flow and light bleeding and in subclinical hyperthyroidism 9 cases had shortened flow. One case had heavy bleeding and 4 had light bleeding irregular cycles for 1 case.

Amenorrhoea is the least reported bleeding pattern in my study. Moulika shah et al [14], Bhavani et al [15] and parveen et al[16] observed similar pattern of menstrual abnormality. It concluded that thyroid disorder should be considered as an important etiological factor for menstrual abnormality.

Thus thyroid profile test should be mandatory in all AUB cases to detect profound and subclinical thy-

roid dysfunction is common. In our study family history of thyroid disorder had strong association with thyroid disorder (0.001) out of 400 cases 29 patients have positive family history. In our study there is significant association of infertility with thyroid disorders. About 26.3% of cases with infertility had hypothyroidism while only 5.2% without infertility had hypothyroidism

Conclusion

From my study it was concluded that, there was a significant association between thyroid disorders and abnormal uterine bleeding. It brought in to attention that increased incidence of hypothyroidism in heavy and prolonged bleeding and also in sub-clinical hypothyroidism. And also found that hyperthyroid cases most common bleeding pattern is shortened and light bleeding. Any type of menstrual disorder should be considered as potential presenting symptoms of thyroid dysfunction and thyroid assessment esteem necessary in these cases, so that we can treat patients at the earliest and prevent morbidities in later life and also can avoid nonspecific and ineffective diagnostic and therapeutic procedures.

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